

A hybrid machine learning model for grade prediction in online engineering education

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Abstract—Facing the disruption caused by COVID-19 pandemic, the emergence of imposed and exclusive online learning revealed challenges for researchers worldwide, as of reforming curricula shortly and of collecting data accumulated by monitoring students' commitment and academic performance. With this pool of data, this research explores grade prediction in a first-semester mechanical engineering CAD module, after testing the performance of the reform of specific curricula. A hybrid model has been created, based on 35 variables having been filtered out of statistical analysis and shown to be strongly correlated to students' academic performance in the specific online module during the first semester of the academic year 2020-2021. The hybrid model consists of a Generalized Linear Model. Its fitting errors are used as an extra predictor to an artificial neural network. The architecture of the neural network can be described by the following sizes: size of the input layer (36), size of the hidden layer (1) and size of the output layer (1). Since new factors are revealed to affect students' academic achievements, the model has been trained in the 70% of the participants to predict the grade of the remaining 30%. The model has therefore been divided into three subsets, with a training set of 70% of the sample and one hidden layer predicting the test set (15%) and the validation set (15%). The final form of the trained hybrid model resulted in a coefficient of determination equal to 1 ($R = 1$). This means that the data fitting process resulted in a 100% success rate, in terms of associating the independent variables with the dependent variable (grade).

Keywords— machine learning, artificial neural network, AI, grade predictive modelling, CAD, COVID-19, online learning, hybrid model

1 Introduction

In recent decades, the use of online and electronic tools made the field of education flourish. As a result, educational applications can be developed to help students access learning material from different geographic locations. Nevertheless, since educational software is provided to a diverse community of students with varying needs and interests, the need for individualization is highlighted [1, 2]. One of the most important aspects of providing education through online methods is the evaluation of learners' results in final examination.

The motivation of this paper emerged during the global outbreak of the COVID-19 virus which has created challenging circumstances for researchers. The imposed online learning in higher education facilitated the accumulation of electronic data screening

students' performance from different backgrounds and geographical locations. In these conditions, it was very interesting to explore the important issue of learners' performance and specifically grade prediction in fully online learning environments.

Although grade prediction through function approximation techniques have been researched in classic learning environments [3], this new reality of merely virtual classrooms and its impact on students' performance in engineering CAD courses has not been analysed adequately yet in terms of grading of engineering students.

The present study presents a Generalized Linear Model (GLM or GLAR-Generalized Linear Regression) that has been created using the 35 most important variables, such as "Succeed in similar future tasks", "Conceive the planes on 3-Dimensional objects", "MS Teams insights" and other. After a data filtering process that will be discussed below, in order to predict students' final exam grades. Its performance is analyzed in two examples of operation, using the errors that derived from the differences between the fitted model and the actual observations. A neural network has been constructed by using the resultant errors of the GLAR model, as an additional predictor (36th).

1.1 Related work

Monitoring students' progress in mechanical engineering CAD courses through grade prediction, has been widely researched when referring to face-to-face and online teaching environments, in order to prevent knowledge loss and dropouts.

Software has been developed to use advanced logic, modelling tools and diagnostic mechanisms to offer a customized learning experience for students, taking into account their learning needs and preferences. Student modelling, can store knowledge about students and then be used to improve the learning experience [4,5]. Information regarding students may include grades, learning attitudes, efforts, perception methods, and other factors. In physical classrooms, educators produce the final grade of the students based on the evaluation of individual tasks and other factors such as the complexity of the activities or their performance on the final exam. Nevertheless, in the area of e-learning this has not been generally and extensively researched [6].

One of the students' focussed initiatives that the learning systems should be focussed, is the early detection of students with lower academic achievements that could potentially fail on a specific module [7]. Many researchers that estimate a student's grade in a future course use neighbourhood-based collaborative filtering method [8, 9, 10, 11]. A group of students with similar performances, who have already attended the module, are assessed to each student whose grade needs to be estimated. Using some similarity-weighted aggregation algorithm, the historical grades of peers are then used to predict the grade that a specific student will receive in a future module enrolment. In [11, 12, 13] the use of sparse linear models and low-rank matrix factorization is suggested for creating a variety of future-course grade prediction methods. These approaches are entirely based on the students' previous module results [14]. In the matrix set up for factorization, the rows represent the students while the columns represent the modules. Each cell contains the grade that the specific student received for each module. Missing values indicate that a student has not yet succeeded in the specific module.

Various approaches for filling in missing values with expected predictions in order to measure an approximation of a potential future grade have been stated in the researches mentioned above. The field of predicting students' grades before the final exams take place have been widely researched [14, 15, 16], while most of those researches apply a variety of data mining algorithms such as Decision Trees, Clustering, Naïve Bayes Classifier and Association Rules. These algorithms use academic performance indicators, such as assignments grades and quizzes marks, instructors' identity in order to predict the grade. Predicting students' nest term performance has also been researched in [15, 16] using SVD and SVD-kNN and Factoring Machine.

Forecasting grades in online educations systems represent a new challenge in the academic community especially during the specific COVID-19 pandemic [17], where in [18] an alternative term has been proposed "Emergency Remote Teaching"¹ and Remote Knowledge acquisition [19]. Researches have indicated specific factors that strongly affect students' academic performance under pandemic circumstances. Those factors, are grouped under constructs, and can be applied as variables in a statistical analysis, in order to be filtered out, estimate their level of significance, as well as their reliability [20].

Concerning the curricula of Mechanical Engineering education, and most specifically regarding first year students, [21] has stated the importance of developing spatial skills. Visualising 3-Dimensional objects enables first year students to develop engineering specific skills. Other researchers [22] stated the link of Engineering education with the society, implementing assignments related to real world tasks and similar to students' future enrolment in their after-graduate employment.

2 Research methodology

This study has been conducted during the first semester of the academic year 2020-2021 in Athens Greece, at the University of West Attica, Faculty of Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering. The module selected is a first semester laboratory course, named "Computer Aided Mechanical Design CAD I". The online module's context has been applied to 216 students which were divided in 11 online groups on the MS Teams platform, assisted by a group of 5 instructors (N=216). The research sample is referring to first year students in order to focus the research on their transition from high school, entrance exams, and first semester in the university, with a valid number of 158 participants (n=158).

Students' performance measuring methods

Valuable information concerning engineering students and their interaction with the learning environment were collected. Data were mined out of two web-based surveys², and additional students' related data including MS Teams' platform insights. Weekly assignments included minds-on tasks: quizzes, sketches [17] (freehand drawings of object views), CAD drawings object views (top views, side views and sectional views).

¹ ERT

² 1. pre-course,2. post-course

Minds-on tasks were aiming to increase students' spatial perception, by introducing innovative methods in task representation (presence of cutting planes in section tasks). Specific tasks were focused on an existing metallic structure (15th assignment), located in a campus building, aiming to estimate the level of students' understanding and its relation to real world tasks in mechanical engineering, and their importance for future employment [23, 24].

Fig. 1. The measuring methods

After processing the collected data, a 129X158 matrix was generated, where the dimension 129 represents the number of the examined variables and 158 the number of students. A statistical analysis has been performed in SPSSv20, including a correlation analysis (Spearman's rank correlation coefficient) for pointing out the most important correlations among all the ordinal variables, a factor analysis (PCA, and via a Varimax type of rotation) and clustering. A reliability analysis has been performed as well and ANOVA has been applied on clusters. The analysis mentioned above filtered out 35 variables that affect students' performance during the disorientated educational process due to COVID-19 pandemic. These 35 variables are highly related to the students' final grade in the CAD I module. The methodology that has been followed is depicted in the following diagram:

Fig. 2. Research methodology

The proposed method in the present study, attempts to combine the advantages of the GLAR method in fitting transformed predictors with a linear logic, with the effectiveness of neural networks in non-linear data fitting applications. In general, neural networks are highly competent in non-linear problems. An artificial neural network (ANN) is a machine learning technique for defining the function that links a set of inputs to a set of outputs. Therefore, a Generalized Linear Model produces a linear combination of transformed predictors (via the response of a link function) as described below.

3 METAMODEL (HYBRID MODEL) FOR STUDENTS' GRADE PREDICTION: USE OF GENERALIZED LINEAR MODEL & NEURAL NETWORK

For the purpose of creating a function to associate the students' performance with the most important variables of the database, a separate file, including them, is created. The function, being created, will have the following form:

$$y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 \dots x_n)$$

Where y is the performance of the students, and x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots are the predictors. In this case, the variables that display a statistically significant relationship with the performance of the student, are used as predictors.

The features of a linear regression model are generalized in a generalized linear regression model. With parameters such as the mean response, the response variable follows a regular, binomial, Poisson, gamma, or inverse Gaussian distribution. The relationship between a dependent variable and the linear combination of altered predictors is defined by a set of link functions that transform each independent variable.

Therefore, a Generalized Linear Model produces a linear combination of transformed predictors (via the response of a link function) with the following form:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \text{intercept}$$

In general, neural networks are highly competent in non-linear problems. An artificial neural network (ANN) is a machine learning technique for defining the function that links a set of inputs to a set of outputs. This is accomplished by connecting the input layer, whose size is proportional to the number of variables being analysed, to an intermediate hidden layer (or a set of hidden layers) that is connected to the output layer. The nodes (or neurons) that make up each layer pass information on to the nodes that come after them. ANNs has been utilized in several research efforts according to related literature [25, 26].

The metamodel neural network's architecture was composed using the methods defined by [27]. The hidden neurons were chosen to have a scale that was between the input and output layers [27].

Fig. 3. Metamodel neural network's architecture

The number of connections (expressed as gradually optimized weights w_{ij}) multiplied by the conveyed output of the previous node i [24] result to each successor node j [28]

$$s_j(x) = \sum_i o_i(x) * w_{ij}$$

The proposed method in the present study, attempts to combine the advantages of the GLAR method in fitting transformed predictors with a linear logic, with the effectiveness of neural networks in non-linear data fitting applications.

A 158x36 matrix is isolated containing the answers and related data of the 158 students in 35 statistically significant variables which display a p-values lower than 5% and whose Spearman rho coefficient is equal to absolute 0.15 or more. The last column (36th) of the table concerns the exam grade of the students.

The followed approach addresses the problem of the lack of tools to deal with ordinal and nominal variables, in multivariate regressions. This is something that does not occur when modelling continuous variables. A hybrid model will be used that combines error prediction resulting from a Generalized Linear Model. Those results are entered as inputs along with a 36th prediction variable (beyond the aforementioned 35 variables), into a neural network for predicting the students' exam grade. All simulations of the present study were performed in MATLAB R2020b.

	ENJOYABLE	FAMILIARISE	EVALUATIO	INSECURE	COMFORTAB	HOWW	ASS	STUDY	STUDY	HOWW	EVALUATE	ES	NECESSITY	CONCEIVE	HELP	ENJOYABLE	LOCK
1	5	5	9	4	3	1	1	6	6	5	5	5	7	5	5	5	5
2	4	4	10	5	3	3	1	5	6	4	4	4	5	4	4	4	5
3	4	4	10	5	5	3	1	7	6	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	5
4	5	1	9	3	3	5	1	4	6	5	3	5	4	4	4	5	5
5	5	4	10	2	4	1	1	7	6	4	3	5	7	2	5	5	5
6	4	3	10	4	3	1	1	3	6	4	3	4	5	3	3	4	5
7	5	5	10	4	4	1	1	4	6	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5
8	5	5	10	3	2	3	1	6	6	4	3	3	7	3	4	4	5
9	2	2	5	1	2	3	1	4	2	4	1	1	4	1	2	4	4
10	3	3	7	3	3	3	1	1	2	4	3	4	5	4	3	2	2
11	5	3	10	5	4	3	1	4	6	4	5	4	1	5	5	5	5
12	5	4	9	3	3	3	1	3	7	5	4	5	7	4	4	4	5
13	5	5	10	5	5	5	1	2	5	4	5	5	3	5	5	5	5
14	5	5	9	4	3	1	1	4	6	5	3	5	4	4	5	5	5
15	5	4	9	5	5	5	1	4	6	5	4	4	4	4	5	5	5
16	4	2	9	1	3	1	1	2	5	4	3	5	5	4	3	4	4
17	4	4	9	5	4	1	1	2	5	4	3	4	7	5	3	4	4
18	5	5	10	3	4	3	1	5	4	6	4	3	5	3	4	5	5
19	4	4	7	2	5	1	5	5	6	5	1	3	3	5	4	4	4
20	5	5	10	4	2	2	5	3	6	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5
21	5	5	10	4	5	1	5	4	6	5	5	5	7	5	5	5	5
22	5	4	9	5	4	3	5	2	6	5	4	5	2	5	5	5	5
23	5	4	8	4	4	1	5	3	6	4	3	4	3	4	2	4	4
24	5	4	8	5	5	1	5	6	6	5	3	4	7	4	5	5	5
25	3	2	3	5	5	1	5	2	7	5	2	2	2	5	5	2	2
26	5	5	9	4	1	1	5	5	6	5	4	4	3	5	5	5	5
27	4	5	10	4	5	1	5	5	6	5	4	5	7	4	4	5	4

Fig. 4. Critical variables isolated to be introduced into MATLAB

The Generalized Linear Model (GLM or GLAR-Generalized Linear Regression) is therefore a flexible generalization of a standard linear regression that allows response variables with non-standard error distribution models. GLM generalizes linear regression by allowing the linear model to relate to the response variable through a link function, which allows the variance of each measurement to be a function of its predicted value. The generalized linear model functions as a way of integrating various other statistical models, such as linear regression, logistic regression and Poisson regression. In its essence, it is a method of iteratively reproducible least squares, and it can maximize the likelihood of model parameters.

An explanation of the process that has been followed, is given below:

- A GLAR model is defined and the corresponding parameters are evaluated. In the examined case, the scores on the 35 variables (e.g.: Evaluation vs other courses, familiarized to MS Teams vs other courses, Conceive the Meaning of Planes etc.) are considered as independent variables and the students' exam grade is the dependent variable. Thus, the response (y) of the model is presented as follows:

$$y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6 \dots x_{35})$$

- The GLAR model processes the linear data. The students' exam grade minus the prediction of the GLAR mode, is considered as a non-linear element. Therefore, what does not result from the GLAR model is considered a non-linear element. That is:

$$error = actual\ grade - predicted\ grade$$

Therefore, the errors resulting from the GLAR model, are shown in the following histogram:

Fig. 5. Histogram of errors resulting from modelling with GLAR

The bin size in the histogram was selected to be equal to 0,5. It can be observed that the errors in the forecast are relatively small. A table analysing the errors along with critical parameters, such as range, mean, median, standard deviation is given below. It can be observed that the mean error is equal to zero.

Statistics		
Error		
N	Valid	158
	Missing	0
Mean		,00000
Median		-,04560
Std. Deviation		,957086
Range		5,349

Table 1. Mean error

It can also be seen that the mean error is equal to zero. The majority of the errors in 109 instances out of the 158 total instances (68.99% of cases), fall into the range between -1 and 1. In 91.77% of cases, the errors fall into the range between -1.5 and 1.5. It is meaningful to note that the range of the grades given to students is between 0 and 10. Below is the table that resulted from the calculation of the coefficient estimates, for the GLAR model that was produced. The coefficient estimates are represented in a relationship that has the following form (Mathworks site):

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_nx_n + intercept$$

Where: $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2 \dots$, are the coefficient estimates from the GLAR model that also denote the significance of each variable.

Table 2. Coefficients, mean standard error, t-test, p-values for the examined independent variables.

Column1	coefficient	Standard error	t-Stat	p-Value
Intercept	3.99	12.810	0.311	75,6%
x1	0.13	0,19008	0.674	50.15%
x2	0.09	0,12503	0.732	46.54%
x3	-0.17	0,097172	-1.793	7.54%
x4	0.07	0,10606	0.670	50.42%
x5	0.00	0,10388	0.042	96.65%
x6	0.09	0,075999	1.127	26.18%
x7	-0.23	0,4594	-0.506	61.34%
x8	-0.01	0,085646	-0.109	91.38%
x9	0.26	0.117	2.260	2.57%
x10	0.32	0,20158	1.597	11.29%
x11	-0.10	0,13195	-0.746	45.68%
x12	0.10	0,14723	0.663	50.87%
x13	-0.07	0,05912	-1.231	22.05%
x14	0.05	0,13144	0.405	68.64%
x15	0.00	0,15607	-0.011	99.13%
x16	-0.04	0,1746	-0.220	82.63%
x17	0.05	0,089314	0.510	61.12%
x18	0.05	0,089286	0.512	60.96%
x19	0.11	0,12427	0.847	39.85%
x20	-0.18	0,17757	-1.017	31.10%
x21	-0.28	0,10915	-2.607	1.03%
x22	0.16	0,13245	1.193	23.53%
x23	-0.04	0,1177	-0.337	73.70%
x24	0.08	0,062739	1.315	19.11%
x25	0.38	0,15466	2.466	1.51%
x26	-0.13	0,1209	-1.063	28.98%
x27	0.02	0,16331	0.140	88.89%
x28	0.08	0,036989	2.138	3.45%
x29	-0.14	0,21164	-0.683	49.56%
x30	-0.06	0,33658	-0.166	86.88%
x31	0.17	0,63535	0.267	78.98%
x32	0.02	0,011321	1.751	8.25%
x33	-0.15	0,11763	-1.269	20.68%
x34	-0.25	0,22524	-1.122	26.40%
x35	-0.45	0,41376	-1.086	27.97%

Table 3. The 35 variables derived from the correlation analysis

Intercept	Variable
x1	Enjoyable vs other labs
x2	Familiarized to MS Teams vs other modules
x3	Evaluation vs other modules
x4	Insecure about CAD I
x5	Comfortable for the finals on CAD I module
x6	How often technical difficulties
x7	Assignments graded and returned after

x8	Study time / week/ hours
x9	Study time During weekday
x10	How well tasks are assessed
x11	Evaluate class notes
x12	How did the quizzes contribute on understanding the theory
x13	Necessity of sketching for understanding the object
x14	Conceive the meaning of planes
x15	Helpful the presence of cutting planes 3-dimensional views
x16	Enjoyable CAD I vs other theoretical modules
x17	Dealing with knowledge deficiencies
x18	Classroom fatigue CAD I
x19	Hours per day on pc for educational purposes including homework
x20	Hours per day on pc attend modules
x21	Resent instructor's late assignment gradings
x22	Noticing weaknesses during CAD I online lectures
x23	Basic computer skills (MS Word, Excel, PowerPoint)
x24	Assignments relevant to future work
x25	Likely succeed in a similar future task
x26	Sustainability of the learning strategy in face-to-face learning
x27	CAD I vs other modules
x28	Physics grades in entrance exams
x29	Number of active students (end)
x30	Number of quitting students
x31	Number of Lectures
x32	Activity MS Teams (insights)
x33	Class group
x34	High school type
x35	Instructor's id
X36	Grade Finals CAD I

The coefficient estimates, (in the column of coefficients) of the 35 examined variables are presented with a color scale, while those that show statistical significance (p-value <5%) are highlighted. The table also displays the mean standard error and statistical t-test of these specific weights (coefficient estimates).

- A neural network model is developed for modelling nonlinear elements, as follows:

$$y_{new} = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, \dots, x_{35}, error)$$
- The results of the combined forecasts will then be obtained.

By sequential tests that were done while running the neural network training process in MATLAB, the number of hidden layers was selected as equal to 1. From the relevant literature [27], the number of hidden layers is recommended to be between the number of input variables (in this case: 36) and the number of output variables (in this case: 1) [29]. This is done to avoid any overfitting of the neural network. Hence, the created neural network can be seen in the following diagram.

Fig. 6. The architecture of the neural network of the hybrid model, Sizes of the input layer (36), the hidden layer (1) and the output layer (1).

The other network hyperparameters (namely: solution algorithm, percentages of the subsets into which the data is divided) as defined in MATLAB, have the following properties: The solution algorithm used was Levenberg-Marquardt, the subset ratio network training was 70%, the validation ratio was 15%, and the network test was 15% [27, 30].

In order for MATLAB to enhance the generalization capabilities of a neural network, the 128 observations are automatically divided into 3 subsets (training, validation and test subset), and the model is trained to fit the main subset (training set). After that, its effectiveness is checked in the other subsets.

The following diagrams are obtained: R (coefficient of determination/ prediction success rate; in this case equal to 1), error histogram (with classification of errors per subset (there are three distinct subsets in the present study: training subset, validation subset, and test subset)) and neural network performance during the training process, which is based on a number of user-defined epochs [27, 30]. The term “epoch” refers to the number of loops the machine learning algorithm has made over the entire dataset.

It should be mentioned that the process of breaking into sets of observations (sets) contributes to the statistical independence of the neural network, since a model resulting from a large set of observations (training set) is used to make predictions for the other subgroups of observations.

Fig. 7. 1 (R) in each subset (training, validation and test set), but also in the sample as a whole.

Fig. 8. Error histogram

Fig. 9. Neural network performance by epoch and by subgroup of observations.

Because the total coefficient of determination is equal to 1, the same applies for all subsets.

The trained model that has been constructed, can be used for prediction purposes of the performance of students that will attend the CAD module in the future. It is evident that by using the trained GLAR model and the 35 variables as predictors, an estimation for the students’ performance can take place. If the error (as a 36th variable) is to be predicted by associating it with other highly correlated and statistically significant variables, the trained hybrid model can be utilized with a similar logic.

3.1 Qualitative analysis and Discussion

In order to interpret the results of the grade prediction process, students with similar predictions and larger differences have been isolated from the sample and evaluated back to the original matrix of the 129 variables (85 ordinal and 44 nominal), out of which 40 of them have shown significant homogeneities and differences among the 6 students. In the following passage, two examples of operations will be presented.

The first example of operation refers to students with higher prediction accuracy.

Student's id	2017	2094	2110	2137	2095	2108	2128
Enjoyable vs other labs	3	3	4	5	4	4	4
Familiarized to MS TEAMS vs other modules	3	3	5	4	3	4	4
Evaluation vs other modules	6	5	10	8	8	9	7
Insecure about CAD I	4	3	4	4	5	3	4
Comfortable for the finals CAD I	4	3	1	4	4	4	3
Technical difficulties	3	1	1	5	1	3	3
Assignments graded & returned after	5	5	5	5	2	2	2
Study time week hours	7	4	6	4	4	5	3
Study time during weekday	6	6	6	6	6	5	6
How well tasks are assessed	4	3	5	4	3	3	4
Evaluate class notes	3	3	3	3	3	3	4

Quizzes contribute understanding theory	4	3	5	4	4	4	4
Necessity of Sketching	7	7	3	5	4	7	5
Conceive the meaning of planes	4	4	5	3	5	4	4
Helpful the presence of cutting planes	5	4	5	4	5	4	4
Enjoyable CAD I vs other theoretical modules	4	3	4	5	3	4	4
Knowledge deficiencies	6	5	5	3	3	5	5
Classroom fatigue	2	1	5	2	3	3	3
Hours/ day pc FOR educational purposes for all modules	4	3	4	3	3	5	4
Hours / day pc attend modules	3	3	3	2	2	3	3
RESENT late Assignments gradings	3	2	5	5	4	3	4
Sense Weaknesses during CAD I	3	5	5	5	5	5	5
BASIC software skills	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Tasks relevant to future work	8	7	7	7	8	9	9
Succeed in a similar future task	3	3	5	4	4	3	4
Sustainability of the framework	4	3	3	3	4	5	3
CAD I vs other modules	2	3	5	5	5	5	4
Physics grades	12	15	18	14	12	10	10
Number of active students at the end	26	26	26	22	24	24	24
Number of quitting students	0	0	0	2	2	2	2
Number of lectures	10	10	10	10	12	12	12
Activity MS Teams	44	41	43	34	41	30	47
Class group	3	3	3	4	6	7	7
Highschool Type	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Instructors' id	1	1	1	1	3	3	3
Grade in CAD I Finals	4.1	4.5	6.1	5.5	4.7	3.7	4.7
Predicted grade (round of 0.0)	4	4.6	6	5.6	4.7	3.6	4.8
Error	0.15	-0.06	0.09	-0.1	-0.02	0.13	-0.12

Table 4. Students with higher prediction accuracy

In the 7 students presented on the table above, the prediction error varies from -0.12 to +0.15.

The second example of operation discusses students with high differences in grade prediction. Student 2080 seem to have a negative attitude towards the learning module due to his resent to distance learning in general. An age difference can be noticed, as of being older than his classmates. His low ratings to most aspects of the online module shows being highly affected by the lack of social distancing (1: extremely discomfortable). He is also negatively affected by technical issues “see Table 4”.

The student considers that the majority of tasks assigned are not relevant to his future work, but understands that the 15th assignment is highly relevant. It can be assumed that since the 15th assignment consists on a CAD drawing of an existing metallic structure, which is represented by video, it establishes a direct relation to real world constructions.

It can be assumed at this point that for the specific student with aversive attitude towards distance learning and being negatively affected by social distancing, certain module’s features related to real world tasks, increased his learning abilities and improved his academic performance. All of the five students expected to acquire higher grades did not download the module’s notes syllabus, but rated highly the CAD I module when compared with other laboratory courses. They expressed being covered by the YouTube MCAD I channel videos. They all do not need to perform freehand

drawings (sketches). They were only sketching during the first lectures, when it was assigned under their weekly tasks. It seems that those students managed to develop their 3-Dimensional conception.

Students' id	2071	2080	2187	2002	2013	2203
Age	18-21	22-25	18-21	18-21	18-21	18-21
Gender	male	male	male	male	male	male
Enjoyable vs other labs	4	2	4	4	5	4
Why like online CAD module	don't like it for all courses	don't like it for all courses	like it, new methods	like it, use of pc	like it, attend from home	like it, attend from home
Evaluation vs other modules	10	5	9	8	8	6
Reason for choosing the faculty	consciously, 1rst choice	consciously, 1rst choice	consciously, 1rst choice	wanted other faculty	consciously, 1rst choice	wanted other faculty
Discomfort of social distancing	2	1	2	1	3	2
Insecure about CAD	not insecure, only for the finals	very insecure to all modules	not insecure at all	not insecure, only for the finals	not insecure at all	not insecure, only for the finals
Meeting new classmates during lectures	no	no	no	yes	no	no
Affected by technical issues	not at all	a lot	not at all	not at all	somewhat	fairly
Assignments' load	normal	normal	normal	normal	not so heavy	not so heavy
Well organised	8	7	9	7	10	8
how well tasks are assigned	very well	very well	very well	very well	extremely well	very well
Times reviewed the theoretical ppt.	read all 1, rarely go through it	read all until the 5th OL lecture	never read them beside OL class	read all 1, often go through it	read all 1, often go through it	read all 1
Download the class notes	no	no	no	no	yes	no
Review CAD notes	not aware of their existence	no	not related to lecture content	no	yes, few times,	covered by lecture & video
necessity of sketching	only for complicated parts	during the first 4 lectures	extremely necessary	only for sectional views	extremely necessary	only for sectional views
part fully perceived in tasks	very well	enough	very well	very well	very well	enough
enjoyable vs other theoretical modules	4	4	4	4	4	4
still sketching during the last lectures	no	no	no	no	no	no

if quit sketching when?	quit sketching on the 6th lecture	quit sketching on the 5th lecture	no, only during the 1st task	quit sketching on the 5th lecture	no, only during the 1st task	quit sketching on the 5th lecture
familiarised to MS Teams	during the first month	still having difficulties after 3 months	during the first month	immediately	during the first month	during the first 2 weeks
Social Media app skills	5	4	3	5	5	4
Tasks relevant to future work	3	8	7	8	8	7
15 th task: presentation and clarity	4	3	3	5	5	4
15 th task relevant to real world	2	4	5	5	5	4
assignments related to real world tasks	2	3	5	4	5	4
likely succeed in a similar future task	somewhat likely	unlikely	extremely likely	very likely	somewhat likely	somewhat likely
Sustainability of the framework	somewhat likely	unlikely	extremely likely	somewhat likely	very likely	somewhat likely
Overall evaluation CAD I	8	4	9	8	8	7
High school type	general lyceum	vocational lyceum	athlete	general lyceum	general lyceum	general lyceum
Activity MS Teams	30	28	3	34	29	15
Assignment grades	1.6	1.4	0.9	2.6	2.4	0.6
Finals' grade	1.1	6.0	5.7	6.6	7.0	5.9
Predicted grade (round of 0.0)	3.4	2.9	3.3	4.0	4.6	2.3
Error	-2.30	3.14	2.44	2.63	2.37	3.59

Table 5. Students with lower prediction accuracy

The critical deviations in errors have an important significance when it comes on deciding if the student will pass the module or not. By taking into consideration that the excellent grade on this exam is 7, the actual grade's range from 3.4 to 7 have been isolated, since an error larger than 1.00 grade is subjected to fail the module.

Fig. 10. Boxplot with mean values and heatmap of errors

A boxplot has been created indicating the mean for the actual grade equal to 5.1 with three outliers, and the mean of the predicted grade at 4.6 which leads to a mean of 0.66 in the error

4 Conclusions

It can be concluded that grade prediction is studied in a variety of ways in literature, and that it can become a valuable component in the process of developing a course recommendation tool, in order to improve students' satisfaction with their own modules' choices. It can also be used as a forecasting tool of potential progress in mandatory modules, as well as a tool to identify modules in which the student is likely to receive poor or even failing grades. Students can even benefit from a pre-course planning of their extracurricular activities during a specific semester where the selected high-risk module will be attended.

Based on the results of this research, critical variables have been revealed concerning factors that affect student's performance in an online first semester engineering CAD I Course, during imposed distance learning circumstances. Even though students have been isolated from their physical learning environment, the applied teaching strategy has managed to relate curricula assignments to real world tasks.

The hybrid model that has been created, used the aforementioned 35 critical variables as predictors. Since imposed distance learning through COVID-19 pandemic started on the second semester of 2020-2021 academic year, the actual research has been focused on a grade forecasting for students of the same period of attendance: The hybrid model has been divided in three subsets, where a training set of 70% of the sample with one hidden layer predicted the test set (15%) and the validation set (15%) applying an automatic grade prediction improvement which led to a fitting of $R=1$.

Future work could consist in testing the performance of those 35 variables to next year first semester students, for the same academic module and examine the level of prediction of the constructed model, in an online or a blended learning environment. A confusion matrix can be created in order to determine the percentage of prediction. In the meanwhile, those variables can be tested at the same population in order to predict their grades on the second semester CAD II module, whose context is a sequence of CAD I and takes place during the second academic semester 2020-2021.

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